

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR L	ELEVATION Min: 63.4647 Max: 63.7115	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1135 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	University of Michigan Walter Reuther Museum of Art Gabii Project
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 0561-570	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #: 148
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DEFINITION Rubble wall - Perpendicular to 1058 - West to East direction	Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU: 1016	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU: 1170	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
Anthropic <input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	Geological <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	Organic <input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry): 1162
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1162, 1058
Is covered by: 1016	Covers:
Is cut by: 1152	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1170

OBSERVATIONS This rubble wall labeled 1135 is approximately 644 cm in length. This measurement includes an approximately 95cm cut by the burial (1150) which intersects the wall approximately 380cm east of its western most point, adjacent to 1058. Current excavated depth is 44cm and the wall appears to be 83cm wide. Average size of rubble is 18x8cm.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: Rubble wall is located in the southern half of the site, originating from the west and continuing east.
Shape: Wall is linear and fairly straight. Its width tends to vary due to current excavation limits and possible collapsed debris. *Observation measurement was taken from widest point.

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight	
Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping	
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular	
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded	
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded	
Observations:	

Handwritten marks: 'u' and 'w' in the bottom left corner of the page.

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: West - East

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions: No mortar visibly present

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) 10cm Medium (range) 18cm Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing: *

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Approx. width: 83cm Approx. length: 644cm

Current Approx. Height: 44cm

Description: The wall originates from the west and continues east for approximately 644cm - at which point current excavation limits obscure eastern end of wall. At the widest point the wall's width is 83cm. Approximately 380cm from the wall's western origin is a burial cut labeled 1150. This burial cut exposes approximately 44cm of the wall's height.

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

1135 is a tufo wall abutting SU:1058. It seems to predate the burial 1150 which was cut into the wall. The wall's relation to the adjacent burial 1125 is undetermined but, 1135 may be a perpendicular extension of another wall feature; located south of SU:1058 and oriented North-South.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by Demaine Francis

on 9/7/10

Revised by CHH

on 12.7.2010

PDFd by

on

Entered by

on